

EBFMC25-OP-56 · Evaluation of Biochemical Parameters in Patients Diagnosed with Hepatosteatosi at the Family Medicine Clinic

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AUTHORS

Begum Saritas Kisalar
<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-4295-9171>

Ilhami Unluoglu
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8130-1443>

AFFILIATIONS

Department of Family Medicine
Faculty of Medicine
Eskisehir Osmangazi University
Eskisehir, Turkey

Department of Family Medicine
Faculty of Medicine
Eskisehir Osmangazi University
Eskisehir, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Introduction: This study was conducted to evaluate the diagnostic performance of certain anthropometric and biochemical parameters as early indicators of NAFLD (non-alcoholic fatty liver disease), aiming to provide practicality in selecting patients suspected of having NAFLD who need further examination and treatment.

Materials and Methods: The study population consists of patients aged 18 and above who visited the Family Medicine Clinic of Eskisehir Osmangazi University Medical Faculty for a check-up between 01.01.2022 and 31.03.2023. 100 patient records meeting the inclusion criteria during this period were identified.

Results: The mean age of the participants included in the study was 55 ± 13.69 , with 57% being female. The average BMI (body mass index) of the patients was 30.32 ± 5.34 kg/m². A significant difference was found between the degrees of hepatosteatosi in terms of insulin ($p=0.019$). The insulin level of the Grade 1 group (11.95 ± 7.19 mIU/L) was statistically significantly lower than that of the Grade 2-3 group (16.63 ± 9.69 mIU/L). A significant difference was found in the HOMA-IR (Homeostasis Model Assessment of Insulin Resistance) values between the degrees of hepatosteatosi ($p=0.002$). The HOMA-IR value of the Grade 1 group (2.96 ± 1.9) was statistically significantly lower than that of the Grade 2-3 group (4.73 ± 2.83).

Conclusion: In our study, a positive correlation was found between NAFLD prevalence and female gender, increasing age, and BMI. As the degree of hepatosteatosi increased, the HOMA-IR value, which indicates insulin resistance, was found to be higher. Considering the possible limitations of non-invasive biomarkers for diagnosing the disease, we believe that in patients with high BMI, insulin resistance, and advanced age, further examinations for hepatosteatosi could lead to earlier detection of NAFLD and reduction in mortality and morbidity with appropriate approaches.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, insulin resistance, obesity, metabolic syndrome

INTRODUCTION

NAFLD (non-alcoholic fatty liver disease) is the most common chronic liver disease worldwide (Angulo, 2002; Bayard et al., 2006). The incidence of NAFLD, which affects approximately 20-30% of the global population, is increasing and is expected to become the leading cause of cirrhosis and liver transplantation in the coming years (Neuschwander-Tetri, 2017). In Turkey, the prevalence of NAFLD is 48.3%, and it rises to 63% in individuals with a BMI (body mass index) ≥ 25 kg/m² (Degertekin et al., 2021). NAFLD is more common in people with diabetes and obesity (Younossi, 2019). With the rising frequency of type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity, and metabolic syndrome, fatty liver disease has become an important problem

(Neuschwander-Tetri, 2017). Hepatosteatosi can progress to steatohepatitis and fibrosis, potentially leading to cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma. As the disease progresses without symptoms, it is often diagnosed only after liver damage has occurred (Yapali & Cicek, 2023). Due to its high prevalence and the potential for progression to cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma, NAFLD has become a significant public health problem (Kalafati et al., 2019). Since NAFLD remains asymptomatic until advanced stages, many patients are only diagnosed at later stages, making risk factor modification and existing or experimental treatments ineffective. Therefore, early predictors need to be investigated (Baranova & Younossi, 2008). Ultrasonography is the primary method used to detect liver fat (Turk Karaciger Arastirmalari Dernegi, 2021). Biopsy is the current gold standard for diagnosis and prognosis, but it is an expensive and invasive procedure with associated complication risks. Due to poor patient acceptance of this invasive technique, there is a need for reliable, accurate, and non-invasive or minimally invasive biomarkers (Piazzolla & Mangia, 2020). This study evaluates the diagnostic performance of certain anthropometric and biochemical parameters as early indicators of NAFLD, investigating whether they can provide practicality in selecting patients suspected of NAFLD.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study population consisted of patients aged 18 and above, who presented for a check-up at the Family Medicine Clinic of Eskisehir Osmangazi University Medical Faculty between 01.01.2022 and 31.03.2023. These patients had hepatosteatosi detected via abdominal ultrasonography and had available biochemical data. Patients with a history of alcohol consumption (more than 20 g/day in women and more than 30 g/day in men) or known chronic liver diseases were excluded. During the specified period, 100 patient records meeting the inclusion criteria were identified. Data were analyzed using SPSS 26.0. t-test, ANOVA, and chi-square tests were used in the analyses. This entire process related to this study has been approved by the Non-interventional Clinical Research Ethics Committee of Eskisehir Osmangazi University with decision number 29 on April 11, 2023.

RESULTS

The mean age of the participants was 55 ± 13.69 , and 57% of them were female. According to ultrasonography results, 68% had Grade 1, 29% had Grade 2, and 3% had Grade 3 hepatosteatosi. Chronic diseases were present in 45% of the patients. Among those with chronic diseases, 29% had hypertension and 12% had diabetes. The average BMI of the patients was 30.32 ± 5.34 kg/m². The proportion of patients with a BMI of 25 and above was 90%. A significant difference in insulin levels was found between the hepatosteatosi grades ($p = 0.019$). The insulin level in the Grade 1 group (11.95 ± 7.19 mIU/L) was statistically significantly lower than in the Grade 2-3 group (16.63 ± 9.69 mIU/L). A significant difference in HOMA-IR (Homeostasis Model Assessment of Insulin Resistance) values was found between the hepatosteatosi grades ($p = 0.002$). The HOMA-IR value in the Grade 1 group (2.96 ± 1.9) was statistically significantly lower than in the Grade 2-3 group (4.73 ± 2.83).

DISCUSSION

The prevalence of NAFLD in women varies between 40-80% in different studies (Angulo et al., 1999; Bacon et al., 1994; Diehl et al., 1998; Itoh et al., 1987; Lee, 1989; Ludwig et al., 1980; Matteoni et al., 1999; Pinto et al., 1996; Powell et al., 1990; Teli et al., 1995). Some studies have also found that it is more common in men (Chen et al., 2008). In our study, NAFLD was found to be more common in women. The literature shows that NAFLD most often appears in the 5th and 6th decades (Angulo et al., 1999; Bacon et al., 1994; Diehl et al., 1998; Itoh et al., 1987; Lee, 1989; Ludwig et al., 1980; Nonomura et al., 1992; Powell et al., 1990). In our study, the average age was found to be 55. Our results were consistent with the literature.

The association between NAFLD and obesity ranges from 30% to 95% in different studies (Angulo et al., 1999; Bacon et al., 1994; Diehl et al., 1998; Itoh et al., 1987; Lee, 1989; Ludwig et al., 1980; Matteoni et al., 1999; Pinto et al., 1996; Powell et al., 1990; Teli et al., 1995). In our study, the proportion of patients with a BMI ≥ 25 was found to be 90%. While the incidence of NAFLD in obese individuals is approximately 75-80%, this rate is around 16% in individuals with normal weight (Milic et al., 2014; Powell et al., 1990). Insulin resistance is the primary factor responsible for the initial insult in the pathogenesis of NAFLD (Bugianesi et al., 2005). A study by Marchesini et al. (1999) found a positive correlation between NAFLD and insulin resistance. In a study consistent with our findings, a positive relationship was found between the level of steatosis and HOMA-IR (Oral & Sahin, 2020). Various studies have found a significant positive correlation

between NAFLD and elevated liver enzyme levels (Chen et al., 2008; Sanyal et al., 2015; Sorbi et al., 1999). In another study, even though liver enzymes were within normal ranges, a positive correlation was found between steatosis levels and liver enzymes (Oz, 2019). In another study, 59% of patients with fatty liver but normal liver enzymes were found to have biopsy-proven non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (Smith & Adams, 2011). In our study, however, no significant difference was found between liver enzyme levels and hepatosteatosis grades. As a result, normal liver enzyme levels are insufficient to exclude a diagnosis of NAFLD, and there is no correlation between the severity of the disease and transaminase levels (Mofrad et al., 2003). Dyslipidemia plays an important role in the etiology of NAFLD. Some studies have found a significant correlation between NAFLD and dyslipidemia, contrary to our findings (Peng et al., 2017; Speliotes et al., 2010). The low number of patients with Grade 3 hepatosteatosis may have contributed to this situation.

CONCLUSION

In our study, the factors directly affecting NAFLD were found to be gender, age, BMI, and insulin resistance. Our study showed that NAFLD is more common in women. Consistent with studies showing that NAFLD emerges more frequently in the 5th and 6th decades of life, the average age in our study was 55. Our study highlighted that increased BMI poses a significant risk for NAFLD and emphasized the importance of weight loss strategies. As the degree of hepatosteatosis increases, the HOMA-IR value also rises. In this context, the study supports the necessity of screening patients for NAFLD in the presence of insulin resistance. There is no correlation between the severity of the disease and liver function tests, and normal liver function tests are insufficient to exclude NAFLD. Due to increased dyslipidemia in NAFLD cases, attention must be paid to the increased cardiovascular risk in these patients.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Begum Saritas Kisalar
Department of Family Medicine
Faculty of Medicine
Eskisehir Osmangazi University
Eskisehir, Turkey
<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-4295-9171>
begumsrt95@gmail.com